

Synthesis and spectral characterisation of high-yield tetracoordinated bis[*N*(1)-alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazole]silver(I) complexes

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Several *N*(1)-alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazoles (L) have been synthesised and reacted with AgNO₃. The ligands are new and *N,N*-chelators. The complexes are isolated as perchlorate salt [AgL₂](ClO₄) (3-5). They are 1 : 1 electrolyte in MeOH and stable in solution (MeOH, CHCl₃) for a long period.

The work stems from our continued interest in the transition metal chemistry of the azoimine ligand systems^{1,2} where imine forms a part of heterocycle. Arylazopyridine (1) are one such system in pyridine backbone which is well-known as a versatile ligand capable of chelating wide range of metal ions^{1,2}. This has encouraged us to find out other heterocycles where arylazo function may be anchored. Imidazole is chosen at the first place because of its ubiquity in chemical and biological systems³. We have synthesised a ligand incorporating arylazo group in imidazole heterocycle known as 2-(arylo)imidazole (2). The exobidentate character of imidazole-*N*(1) is restricted by alkylation, and its coordination chemistry^{4,5} and analytical application⁶ are described elsewhere. The richness of this chemistry has encouraged to initiate research on the chemistry of silver involving this ligand system.

The coordination chemistry of silver is well established and the coordination number is very much sensitive to the nature of the ligand and anions. Ligands with donor atoms P, As, S, Se etc. give many complexes; those are mostly dimeric/polymeric⁷. Although silver(I) forms a great variety of complexes with *N*-donors but the reports on high-yield stable, monomeric compounds of silver(I) with chelated ligands are scanty^{2,7,8}. The chemistry of monomeric silver(I) complexes of bidentate *N,N*-donors has grown around 2,2'-bipyridine and related ligands⁹ and recently, complexes of other *N,N*-donors systems appear in literature^{2,10}.

In this report we describe the high-yield synthesis of stable, monomeric tetracoordinated silver(I) complexes of *N*(1)-alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazoles (L). The structure assessment and the stability of the complexes in solution have been made on the basis of spectral data.

Results and Discussion

The ligands used are *N*(1)-alkyl-2-(7/8-substituted-arylo)imidazole and abbreviations of *N*(1)-methyl, *N*(1)-ethyl and *N*(1)-benzyl-2-(arylo)imidazoles are MeL, EtL and BzL respectively. The ligands are new and their melt-

ing temperature is less than that of precursor *N*(1)-H derivatives (2). This may be due to hydrogen bonding network in the precursor¹¹. The ligands are *N,N*-chelating type and react with AgNO₃ in boiling MeOH in the metal-ligand ratio 1 : 2 to yield cationic [AgL₂]⁺ ([Ag(MeL)₂]⁺ 3, [Ag(EtL)₂]⁺ 4 and [Ag(BzL)₂]⁺ 5 and isolated as their perchlorate salt. The complexes were characterised by C, H, N and Ag analyses which confirmed the 1 : 2 metal-ligand composition. Silver analyses were carried out gravimetrically¹² and the experimental results are within acceptable error range (<3%). The complexes are soluble in common polar organic solvents as well as in CHCl₃, CH₂Cl₂ but insoluble in nonpolar benzene, hexane etc. The molar conductance of the complexes lies between 90 and 110 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, suggesting a 1 : 1 type electrolytic nature of the compounds^{2,4}. The results collectively conform to the formulation of the compounds as [AgL₂](ClO₄).

IR spectra of 2-(arylo)imidazoles exhibit a broad medium intense band for N-H stretch at ~3340 cm⁻¹ and disappears on alkylation. The ν_{N=N} and endocyclic ν_{C=N} appear at around 1400 and 1600 cm⁻¹ respectively. Imidazole ring stretching modes appear at 1480-1400, 780-

Table 1 Electronic and ^1H nmr spectral data*

Compd no.	λ_{max} , nm ($10^{-3}\epsilon$, $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	δ							
		4-H ^d	5-H ^d	7-H	8-H	9-H ^h	10-H ^h	11-H ^c	12-H
3a	454(4.53), 386(21.70)	7.58	7.32	2.63 ^f	7.21 ^c	7.24	7.38	7.56	4.22 ⁱ
b	422(3.24), 380(18.92)	7.51	7.28	3.94 ^g	7.00 ^c	7.18	7.28	7.50	4.20 ⁱ
c	458(4.31), 388(22.50)	7.57	7.30	–	7.33 ^e	7.28	7.45	7.58	4.24 ^h
d	465(4.58), 390(23.18)	7.60	7.32	–	7.68 ^e	7.33	7.57	7.62	4.26 ^h
e	447(3.81), 387(16.51)	7.52	7.30	7.55 ^d	2.40 ^f	7.20	7.42	7.62	4.24 ^f
4a	458(5.30), 382(32.90)	7.56	7.33	2.61 ^f	7.20 ^e	7.25	7.39	7.59	4.56 ⁱ 1.68 ^k
b	425(3.89), 377(26.68)	7.52	7.30	3.92 ^g	7.01 ^e	7.18	7.30	7.52	4.55 ⁱ 1.65 ^k
c	460(4.59), 385(26.49)	7.58	7.30	–	7.35 ^e	7.30	7.44	7.60	4.62 ^j 1.60 ^k
d	452(4.29), 385(28.42)	7.60	7.33	–	7.70 ^e	7.35	7.55	7.63	4.68 ^j 1.69 ^k
e	443(5.71), 380(32.84)	7.54	7.30	7.63 ^d	2.42 ^f	7.22	7.43	7.64	4.45 ^j 1.60 ^k
5a	455(3.87), 380(25.55)	7.50	7.31	2.64 ^f	7.14 ^e	7.29	7.36	7.56	5.70 ⁱ
b	427(3.08), 380(20.16)	7.52	7.28	3.95 ^g	7.00 ^e	7.20	7.28	7.49	5.70 ⁱ
c	455(4.12), 386(20.84)	7.55	7.28	–	7.30 ^e	7.27	7.47	7.58	5.73 ⁱ
d	458(4.66), 385(30.19)	7.58	7.30	–	7.65 ^e	7.33	7.58	7.63	5.70 ⁱ
e	446(4.14), 380(25.46)	7.55	7.26	7.52 ^d	2.44 ^f	7.30	7.42	7.60	5.72 ⁱ

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses ^bIn CHCl_3 , ^cIn CDCl_3 , ^dSinglet, ^eDoublet (J 7.6–8.0 Hz), ^f δ (Ar-OMe) ^g δ (Ar-OMe), ^hTriplet (J 7.5–8.0 Hz), ⁱ δ (N-Me), ^j δ (12 CH_2) in $\text{N-CH}_2\text{CH}_3$ (quartet, J 9.0–11.0 Hz) ^k δ ($^{13}\text{CH}_3$) in $\text{N-CH}_2\text{CH}_3$ (triplet, J 8.0 Hz) ^l δ (N- CH_2 -Ph), singlet

790, 740–750 and 650–600 cm^{-1} in the compounds⁴. In $[\text{AgL}_2](\text{ClO}_4)$ the $\nu_{\text{N}=\text{N}}$ appears at 1385–1375 cm^{-1} and the red-shifting ($\Delta\nu = 15\text{--}25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) attributes to azo-N coordination^{2,4}. All the complexes exhibit a structureless band at around 1090 and 625 cm^{-1} corresponding to ν_{ClO_4} , suggesting lack of significant perchlorate coordination in the solid state.

The solution electronic spectra of the ligands and complexes were recorded in CHCl_3 . The ligands exhibit three spectral transitions within 500–220 nm; a weak absorption at 420–440 nm followed by two strong transitions at 370–375 and 270–280 nm. These are assigned as intraligand charge transfer ($n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$) transitions. In complexes $[\text{AgL}_2](\text{ClO}_4)$, the bands suffer small bathochromic shift (Table 1) and indicates a weak interactions^{2,4} between ligand and Ag^+ . The silver complexes obey Beer's law in both CHCl_3 and MeOH. The intensity of the bands do not change with dilution. Hence, $[\text{AgL}_2]^+$ ion is stable in these solvents.

The bonding mode is established by ^1H nmr spectra. The spectra were collected in CDCl_3 and data are given in Table 1. The 7-Me and 7-OMe signals appear at δ 2.6 and 3.9 respectively, while 8-Me appears at δ 2.4. The downfield shifting of the former may be due to nearer posi-

tion of azo function. Other aryl protons are assigned on the basis of chemical shift, spin-spin splitting and changes therein on substitution. The 8-H is effected severely in (a-d) on substitution and the shifting is quite expected in view of inductive and electronic effect of the substituents^{4,5}. The 7-H signal appears as a singlet in (e). The signal due to 11-H appears relatively at downfield position followed by 10-H resonance. Imidazolic 4-H suffers sever downfield shifting (7.6 ppm) compared to free ligand value ($\delta_{4\text{-H}}$ 7.2–7.3), while 5-H shifts (7.3 ppm) slightly in the same direction (free ligand value $\delta_{5\text{-H}}$ 7.1–7.2). This may be due to the coordination of N(3) to Ag^+ where 4-H is nearer than 5-H^{4,5}. 2-(Arylazo)imidazoles exhibit broad resonance at $\delta \sim 10.4$ corresponding to N-H resonance which is estimated on N(1)-alkylation. The N(1)-Me in $[\text{Ag}(\text{MeL})_2](\text{ClO}_4)$ (3) appears as singlet at δ 4.2; N(1)- $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_3$ in $[\text{Ag}(\text{EtL})_2](\text{ClO}_4)$ (4) shows a quartet at δ (CH_2) 4.6 (J 9.0–11.0 Hz) and a triplet at δ (CH_3) 1.6 (J 8.0 Hz), and N(1)- $\text{CH}_2\text{-Ph}$ in $[\text{Ag}(\text{BzL})_2](\text{ClO}_4)$ (5) shows a singlet at δ (CH_2) 5.7. The corresponding free ligand values are MeL : δ (CH_3) 4.0; EtL : δ (CH_2) 4.4 and δ (CH_3) 1.5 and BzL : δ (CH_3) 5.5. Phenyl protons (14–18-H) in $\text{N-CH}_2\text{Ph}$ appear as a multiplet at δ 7.3–7.4.

It is noted that all the protons in the aliphatic and aromatic regions exhibit only one signal (singlet or multi-

plet) for each proton. This suggests that both the chelate rings in the complexes are magnetically equivalent at least on the nmr time-scale and the complexes contain the effective C_2 -axis which is in agreement with the AgN_4 tetrahedral coordination sphere.

Experimental

Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on Perkin-Elmer 783 and 883 spectrophotometers and 1H nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) on Bruker 200 and 300 MHz FT-NMR spectrometers using TMS as internal standard. The solution electrical conductivity was measured using a Systronics 304 digital conductivity meter. The microanalytical data were obtained from a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNO/S analyser. Silver analysis was carried out gravimetrically¹². Beer's law verification of the solutions of $[Ag(MeL_a)_2](ClO_4)$ was tested using $\sim 10^{-4}$ M concentration spectrophotometrically in both MeOH and $CHCl_3$.

o-Methyl-, *o*-methoxy- and *m*-methylanilines (SRL), *o*-chloro- and *o*-nitroanilines (Fluka), imidazole and $AgNO_3$ (Glaxo) and $NaClO_4$ (E. Merck) were used. The ligands 2-(aryloxy)imidazoles were obtained by diazo-coupling of aryldiazonium chloride with imidazole in Na_2CO_3 solution (pH 7) and purified by reported procedures^{4,5}: 2-((7-methyl)phenylazo)imidazole (**2a**), m.p. $162 \pm 1^\circ$; 2-((7-methoxy)phenylazo)imidazole (**2b**), $129 \pm 1^\circ$, 2-((7-chloro)phenylazo)imidazole (**2c**), $179 \pm 2^\circ$; 2-((7-nitro)phenylazo)imidazole (**2d**), $152 \pm 2^\circ$ and 2-((8-methyl)phenylazo)imidazole (**2e**), $142 \pm 2^\circ$.

N(1)-Methyl-2-((7-methyl)phenylazo)imidazole (MeL_a): To dry THF solution of **2a** (0.75 g, 4.03 mmol), NaH (50% paraffin) (0.35 g) was added in small portions and stirred at cold condition for 0.5 h. Methyl iodide was then added slowly for a period of 1 h and warmed at 60° for another 1 h. The solution was evaporated, extracted with $CHCl_3$, washed with 10% NaOH (3×10 ml) and finally with distilled water (3×20 ml). It was chromatographed over silica gel prepared in benzene and the desired compound was eluted by MeCN- C_6H_6 (1 : 19, v/v). The orange crystalline needles were separated on slow evaporation (0.48 g, 45%). Other alkylated products were prepared following the same general route in the yields 35–50%: MeL_a , m.p. $88 \pm 1^\circ$; MeL_b , gum; MeL_c , $98 \pm 2^\circ$; MeL_d , $118 \pm 1^\circ$; MeL_e , gum; EtL_a , gum; EtL_b , gum; EtL_c , gum; EtL_d , $106 \pm 2^\circ$; EtL_e , gum; BzL_a , $92 \pm 1^\circ$; BzL_b , $81 \pm 1^\circ$; BzL_c , gum; BzL_d , $96 \pm 2^\circ$; BzL_e , $75 \pm 2^\circ$.

Bis[*N*(1)-methyl-2-((7-methyl)phenylazo)imidazole]silver(i) perchlorate, $[Ag(MeL_a)_2](ClO_4)$ (**3a**): A solution of $AgNO_3$ (0.085 g, 0.5 mmol) in MeOH (10 ml) was added

slowly to a stirred solution (10 ml) of MeL_a (0.2 g, 1 mmol) and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. On cooling, orange-yellow precipitate appeared. It was further heated to redissolve the precipitate and filtered hot. To it an aqueous solution of $NaClO_4$ (1 g in 10 ml) was added with constant stirring. The resulting dark orange-brown solid was washed with water, crystallised from MeOH- H_2O (3 : 1, v/v), dried under reduced pressure over P_4O_{10} and preserved at dark, yield 75%.

Other silver(i) complexes were prepared following the same procedure, yields 65–80%.

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